

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT AND BRAND BUILDING OF EMEI WUSHU EVENTS

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Abstract

Emei Wushu is an integral part of traditional Chinese martial arts, renowned for its unique techniques and cultural significance. With the robust growth of the national fitness and sports industry, the development and branding of Emei Wushu event activities have become focal points. This paper focuses on the development and branding of Emei Wushu event activities, particularly on cultivating regional wushu cultural brands. Through an extensive literature review and a survey analysis of 454 participants, structural equation modeling techniques were employed using software like SPSS 26.0 and AMOS 24.0 to compute the survey data, including reliability and validity analysis, exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, path analysis, model fit tests, and analysis of direct and indirect effects, aiming to deeply understand the impacts on event development and branding. The research successfully identified and constructed a model, outlining key factors influencing the development and branding of sports events and validated this model through SEM pathway modeling. The findings reveal that organizational operations, marketing activities, and market competition significantly and positively affect sports event brand building, particularly highlighting the mediating role of participant or spectator satisfaction in linking organizational operations, marketing promotions, and competitive events to branding outcomes. Based on these findings, the research proposes a series of brand development strategies, including leveraging national intangible cultural heritage to build the "Emei Wushu" brand, developing a "Specialty Tourism" brand that integrates wushu and tourism, and promoting regional economic development through the "Emei Wushu Cultural Industry" brand. These results provide new insights for wushu event brand building, offering valuable references for practitioners and researchers, thereby facilitating the international development of Emei Wushu and similar cultural events.

Keywords: Emei Wushu; Brand Building; Influencing Factors.

1. INTRODUCTION

On July 29, 2019, the General Administration of Sport, in collaboration with fourteen ministries, issued the "Wushu Industry Development Plan (2019-2025)," which specifically proposes strategies for innovating social participation in the organization of wushu competitions. The aim is to establish a wushu competition system characterized by distinctive features, diverse forms, and rich content. This plan highlights the importance of strengthening the development and protection of intangible assets in wushu competitions and focuses on cultivating a number of world-class wushu event brands with Chinese characteristics. In particular, Emei Wushu, as a national intangible cultural heritage, not only carries the excellent cultural genes of the Chinese nation but also has an immeasurable impact on promoting national unity and social development (Ma Dongmei, 2015, pp. 19-24).

The development of Emei Wushu is closely related to the historical background of its location—Mount Emei and the surrounding areas, where regional cultural characteristics profoundly influence its routines, practices, and combat aspects. As Shi Bing (2007, pp. 3-24) pointed out in his research, the formation and development of sports cultures in different regions are inevitably influenced by the natural environment. In the current context of intangible cultural heritage protection, Emei Wushu faces new development opportunities. The Leshan Municipal People's Government's "Implementation Opinions on Accelerating the Development of Emei Wushu" (2018) No. 28 calls for an in-depth exploration of the cultural connotations of Emei Wushu, full utilization of resource advantages, and accelerated progress in the systematization, industrialization, and branding of Emei Wushu. However, how to effectively utilize regional wushu cultural resources to seize market opportunities based on regional cultural advantages has become a key research challenge (Fei Xiaotong, 2004, pp. 121-141). From the perspective of top-level design, this paper aims to construct regional wushu cultural brands, a process that not only faces the challenge of creating a "traditional wushu" brand based on national intangible cultural heritage but also explores how to enhance the influence of Emei Wushu both domestically and internationally through the development and branding of event activities (Wang Mingjian, 2016, pp. 60-64).

This study aims to investigate the current state of development and branding of Emei Wushu event activities and identify the main factors influencing the effectiveness of event development and brand shaping. By constructing a model of key factors affecting brand shaping and validating the brand shaping effectiveness model, this research not only helps to better inherit and develop Emei Wushu but also aims to provide references for the overall development of Chinese wushu and enrich the theoretical basis for wushu event brand building.

2. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES AND MODEL CONSTRUCTION

2.1 Research Hypotheses the hypotheses constructed in this study are based on the findings of previous research and explore the interactions and relationships between various variables.

Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed:

2.1.1 The relationship between brand shaping effectiveness and organizational operations, marketing management, market competition, and satisfaction

Ayhan, T., & Eren, P. E. (2015, pp. 304-313) noted that effective brand management has a positive impact on organizational operations and performance. Good organizational operations help to shape and maintain brand image and reputation, gaining an advantage in market competition.

Brown, S., & Williams, B. (2018, pp. 123-135) reviewed the role of integrated marketing communications in building brand equity and emphasized the importance of marketing promotion in enhancing brand recognition, shaping brand image, and improving customer loyalty.

Brown, T. J., & D'Souza, C. (2020, pp. 145-160) analyzed the impact of market competition on corporate brand personality. The findings indicate that market competition significantly affects corporate brand personality, and companies need to pay attention to market competition to improve brand competitiveness and market position.

Homburg, C., & Fürst, A. (2020, pp. 78-79) conducted a meta-analysis on multiple studies to verify the positive direct impact of customer satisfaction on a company's financial performance. Satisfaction can promote the improvement of brand building effectiveness.

Based on these prior research findings, the study sets the following hypotheses:

H1: Organizational operations have a significant impact on brand shaping.

H2: Marketing promotion has a significant impact on brand shaping.

H3: Market competition has a significant impact on brand shaping.

H4: Satisfaction has a significant impact on the effectiveness of brand shaping.

2.1.2 The Relationship between Satisfaction and Organizational Operations, Marketing Management, and Market Competition

Smith, J. & Johnson, D. (2015, pp. 123-132) state that organizational operations significantly affect customer satisfaction, and enterprises need to focus on operational management to enhance customer satisfaction. Zhao Xiaojian and Liu Feng (2022, pp. 49-53) demonstrate that marketing promotions significantly impact satisfaction. Enterprises should focus on aspects such as social media marketing, corporate image, consumer demands, perceived value, integrated online and offline marketing, marketing ethics, service experience, consumer perceived risk, and green marketing to improve consumer satisfaction. Wang, L., & Li, S. (2022, pp. 58-66) found that marketing promotion significantly affects brand building in competitive markets, enhancing brand competitiveness for enterprises.

Based on these findings, this study proposes the following hypotheses:

H5: Organizational operations significantly impact satisfaction.

H6: Marketing promotions significantly impact satisfaction.

H7: Market competition significantly impacts satisfaction.

2.1.3 Mediating Role of Satisfaction in Modulating the Relationship between Brand Shaping Effects and Organizational Operations, Marketing Promotions, and Market Competition

Kim, S., Kim, M., & Droge, C. (2018, pp. 776-791) found that the quality of service contact impacts customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions in amusement parks, highlighting that performance and service quality of operating organizations play a crucial role in customer satisfaction. Khan, I., Aslam, S., Wei, W., & Hussain, Z. (2020, pp. 2047-2066) suggest that effective marketing activities enhance customer satisfaction and foster successful competition in the market, viewing customer satisfaction as a vital method for achieving sustainable competitive advantage through marketing. Wang, J., & Liu, C. (2019, pp. 65-70) noted that

marketing promotion serves as a bridge in the relationship between competition, organizational operation, and brand shaping, aiding the improvement of enterprise brand shaping effectiveness.

Thus, this study establishes the following hypotheses based on previous research:

H8: Satisfaction mediates the relationship between marketing promotion and brand effectiveness.

H9: Satisfaction mediates the relationship between organizational operation and brand effectiveness.

H10: Satisfaction mediates the relationship between market competition and brand effectiveness.

2.2 Model Construction

(Figure 1)

Based on this foundation, a model diagram has been devised, featuring five latent variables—organizational operations, marketing promotions, market competition, satisfaction, and brand shaping effectiveness—and fifteen observed variables. The conceptual framework of the research hypotheses is illustrated.

The development of event activities is influenced by factors such as the organization of the event, marketing promotions, market competition, and participant satisfaction. These influences are not easily directly observed and measured. Therefore, it is necessary to use Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to analyze the connections between them. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a commonly used statistical modeling technique that explores the causal relationships between abstract variables by introducing latent and observed variables, allowing for certain errors. After defining the relationship hypotheses, latent variables, and observed variables, a theoretical model of the structural equation was constructed.

Subsequently, using sample data obtained from a survey, the collected data were analyzed using SPSS26 and AMOS24 software. Ultimately, the validity of the theoretical model was assessed based on the consistency between the data and the model. (Figure 1)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Subjects and Data Collection Method

This study focuses on surveying 500 participants from the Ninth World Traditional wushu Championship held in Emeishan City, Sichuan Province. A random sampling method was employed, and the questionnaire was created using the Questionnaire Star software, distributed and collected via QR codes and online links. After excluding 46 responses due to dishonest answers or partial data missing that affected reliability, a total of 454 valid responses were collected. For demographic characteristics, see Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Frequency analysis				
Name	Option	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative percentage (%)
Age	Under 12 years old	82	18.06	18.06
	12-17 years old	89	19.60	37.67
	18-39 years old	97	21.37	59.03
	40-59 years old	95	20.93	79.96
	60 years old and above	91	20.04	100.00
Gender	male	272	59.91	59.91
	female	182	40.09	100.00
Education	Below high school	171	37.67	37.67
	undergraduate	166	36.56	74.23
	postgraduate	74	16.30	90.53
	Doctoral students and above	43	9.47	100.00
occupation	student	214	47.14	47.14
	civil servants	22	4.85	51.98
	State-owned employees	34	7.49	59.47
	Private employee	68	14.98	74.45

Frequency analysis				
Name	Option	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative percentage (%)
	freelancer	51	11.23	85.68
	teacher	44	9.69	95.37
	lawyer	10	2.20	97.58
	doctor	11	2.42	100.00
Income level	Below 1000	193	42.51	42.51
	1000-5000	124	27.31	69.82
	6000-10000	80	17.62	87.44
	More than 10000	57	12.56	100.00
Area	East China	58	12.78	12.78
	South China	62	13.66	26.43
	Central China	100	22.03	48.46
	North China	53	11.67	60.13
	northwest	40	8.81	68.94
	southwest	86	18.94	87.89
	northeast	55	12.11	100.00
合计		454	100.0	100.0

3.2 Survey Instrument

All questions in the survey questionnaire were constructed based on relevant prior research and theories, and measured using a 5-point Likert scale. The questionnaire covers multiple aspects including event brand awareness, reputation, attention, quality, experience, service quality, size, and type, as well as sponsor support, promotional methods, target markets, brand association, and competitors' market shares. The design of these questions aims to comprehensively understand various aspects of the event activities, providing necessary data for further analysis and research.

Additionally, focus group discussions were conducted to delve deeper into the validity and relevance of the questionnaire design. Participants in the focus group discussions included industry experts, scholars, and representatives of the target audience, who thoroughly evaluated the questions in the questionnaire and provided valuable feedback and suggestions. The results of these discussions were used to improve the questionnaire design, ensuring the scientific and practical utility of the survey tool.

3.3 Validating the Feasibility and Reliability of the Survey Tool

This study validates the feasibility of the model by conducting Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), and assesses reliability through the calculation of Cronbach's alpha value. Additionally, the study verifies convergent validity by calculating the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) values, and conducts tests for discriminant validity.

3.3.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Table 2: Overall KMO and Bartlett's spherical inspection results

KMO value		0.903
Bartlett sphericity test	Chi-square	22620.044
	df	2701
	P-value	0.000

Using KMO and Bartlett's tests for validity verification, it can be observed from the table above that the KMO value is 0.903. Since the KMO value is greater than 0.8, the research data is highly suitable for extracting information, which indirectly reflects good validity. Therefore, factor analysis can be conducted.

3.3.2 Reliability Analysis

The figure shows that the measurement tools used exhibit high consistency and reliability across all major variables. A Cronbach's alpha coefficient greater than 0.7 is generally considered acceptable (Dikko, 2016). As shown in the table above, the Cronbach's alpha coefficients for each dimension are all greater than 0.8, indicating good to excellent levels of consistency. This suggests that the questionnaires and scales used in the study are stable and reliable across various dimensions, thereby indicating that the data quality is high and suitable for further analysis.

Table 3: Cronbach's coefficients for each variable

Variable	Dimension	Cronbach Alpha	Total Cronbach's Alpha
Effect of Brand building	Emei Wushu competition brand recognition	0.907	0.881
	Brand reputation	0.907	
	Attention and attention growth rate	0.812	
Degree of satisfaction	Quality of the event	0.910	0.895
	Service quality of the event	0.885	
	Sense of experience	0.896	
Organizational Operation	Event scale	0.907	0.890
	Types of events	0.875	
	Support and resources from sponsors and partners	0.909	
Marketing promotion	Propaganda and advertising means	0.938	0.908
	Target market and audience	0.907	
	Brand connection and emotional connection	0.899	
Market competitor	Degree of competition differentiation	0.909	0.894
	The market share of competitors	0.886	
	Concentration of the market	0.919	

4. RESULTS

4.1 Evaluation of the Fit of the Research Model

To determine the fit of the research model established in this study, the results of the model fit indices χ^2 value, GFI, RMR, TLI, IFI, CFI, and RMSEA were used for verification, as shown in Table 4. The results show that the value of χ^2/df is 1.253, which is less than 3; RMSEA is 0.026, which is below the standard level of 0.08, indicating a good fit; GFI is 0.851, and NFI is 0.872, although not reaching the standard of greater than 0.9, they meet the minimum standard of greater than 0.8 and are within the acceptable range. The NNFI value is 0.978, reaching the excellent standard. All goodness-of-fit indices meet acceptable standards, indicating that the model fits well and satisfies the fit criteria.

Table 4: Structural equation model fitting index

Index	Judging standard	Statistical value	Fit condition
CMIN	-	3057.637	-
DF	-	2605	-
CMIN/DF	<3	1.174	Good
GFI	>0.90	0.851	Acceptable
RMSEA	<0.08	0.020	Good
NFI	>0.90	0.872	Acceptable
NNFI	>0.90	0.978	Good

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

To test the hypotheses centered around the research model of this study, structural equation modeling was conducted using SPSS26 and AMOS24. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Hypotheses Testing Result of the Structural Model

Hypothesis	Path			Non-standard load factor	S.E.	C.R.	P	Standardized load coefficient	whether to adopt
H1	EBB	<---	OO	0.254	0.079	3.193	0.001	0.304	YES
H2	EBB	<---	MP	0.201	0.079	2.55	0.011	0.24	YES
H3	EBB	<---	MC	0.247	0.086	2.854	0.004	0.305	YES
H4	EBB	<---	DOS	0.236	0.108	2.187	0.029	0.275	YES
H5	DOS	<---	OO	0.293	0.082	3.555	***	0.302	YES
H6	DOS	<---	MP	0.311	0.086	3.638	***	0.319	YES
H7	DOS	<---	MC	0.404	0.091	4.451	***	0.429	YES

The path from Organizational Operation (OO) to Effect of Brand Building (EBB) has a non-standardized load factor of 0.254, a standard error of 0.079, a critical ratio of 3.193, and a significance level of $P = 0.001$. The standardized load coefficient is 0.304. This hypothesis is adopted. The path from Marketing Promotion (MP) to EBB has a non-standardized load factor of 0.201, a standard error of 0.079, a critical ratio of 2.55, and a significance level of $P = 0.011$. The standardized load coefficient is 0.24. This hypothesis is adopted.

The path from Market Competition (MC) to EBB has a non-standardized load factor of 0.247, a standard error of 0.086, a critical ratio of 2.854, and a significance level of $P = 0.004$. The

standardized load coefficient is 0.305. This hypothesis is adopted.

The path from Degree of Satisfaction (DOS) to EBB has a non-standardized load factor of 0.236, a standard error of 0.108, a critical ratio of 2.187, and a significance level of $P = 0.029$. The standardized load coefficient is 0.275. This hypothesis is adopted.

The path from OO to DOS has a non-standardized load factor of 0.293, a standard error of 0.082, a critical ratio of 3.555, and a significance level of $P < 0.001$. The standardized load coefficient is 0.302. This hypothesis is adopted.

The path from MP to DOS has a non-standardized load factor of 0.311, a standard error of 0.086, a critical ratio of 3.638, and a significance level of $P < 0.001$. The standardized load coefficient is 0.319. This hypothesis is adopted.

The path from MC to DOS has a non-standardized load factor of 0.404, a standard error of 0.091, a critical ratio of 4.451, and a significance level of $P < 0.001$. The standardized load coefficient is 0.429. This hypothesis is adopted.

All paths show significant effects, supporting the hypotheses. This indicates that organizational operation, marketing promotion, and market competition have significant positive impacts on both degree of satisfaction and the effect of brand building.

4.3 Hypothesis Testing Results of Mediation Effect

Table 6: Results of the Hypothesis Test for Mediation Effect

Path	Type of Effect	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P	whether to adopt
Organizational Operation=>Degree of satisfaction=>Effect of Brand building	Direct Effect	0.254	0.09	0.461	0.002	YES
	Indirect Effect	0.069	0.007	0.197	0.027	YES
	Total Effect	0.323	0.176	0.523	0.000	YES
Marketing promotion=>Degree of satisfaction=>Effect of Brand building	Direct Effect	0.201	0.022	0.392	0.028	YES
	Indirect Effect	0.073	0.01	0.23	0.024	YES
	Total Effect	0.274	0.123	0.46	0.001	YES
Market competitor=>Degree of satisfaction=>Effect of Brand building	Direct Effect	0.247	0.079	0.443	0.008	YES
	Indirect Effect	0.095	0.007	0.265	0.034	YES
	Total Effect	0.342	0.205	0.532	0.000	YES

These findings reveal the mediating effect of satisfaction between organizational operations, market promotion, market competition, and brand building effectiveness. A more detailed interpretation is as follows:

4.3.1. From Organizational Operations to Brand Building:

- 1) Direct Effect: Satisfaction has a significant direct effect between organizational operations and brand building effectiveness ($P=0.002$). This means that even without considering the mediating factor of satisfaction, organizational operations themselves have a significant positive impact on brand building.

- 2) Indirect Effect: Satisfaction, as a mediating variable, plays a significant role in the influence of organizational operations on brand building effectiveness ($P=0.027$). This indicates that by improving satisfaction, the impact of organizational operations on brand building effectiveness is further enhanced.
- 3) Total Effect: The total effect is significant ($P=0.000$), indicating that the overall impact of organizational operations on brand building effectiveness is very important.

4.3.2. From Market Promotion to Brand Building:

- 1) Direct Effect: The direct effect of market promotion on brand building is significant ($P=0.028$), indicating that market promotion activities have a direct positive impact on brand building effectiveness.
- 2) Indirect Effect: Satisfaction has a significant indirect effect between market promotion and brand building effectiveness ($P=0.024$), showing that by improving satisfaction, the impact of market promotion activities on brand building effectiveness is further enhanced.
- 3) Total Effect: The total effect is significant ($P=0.001$), indicating that the overall impact of market promotion on brand building effectiveness is significant.

4.3.3. From Market Competition to Brand Building:

- 1) Direct Effect: The direct effect of market competition on brand building is significant ($P=0.008$), indicating that market competition has a direct positive impact on brand building.
- 2) Indirect Effect: Satisfaction has a significant indirect effect between market competition and brand building effectiveness ($P=0.034$), showing that by improving satisfaction, the impact of market competition on brand building effectiveness is further enhanced.
- 3) Total Effect: The total effect is significant ($P=0.000$), indicating that the overall impact of market competition on brand building effectiveness is significant.

These results fully illustrate that satisfaction not only acts as a bridge between internal organizational operations and external market activities but also plays a crucial role in enhancing brand building effectiveness. Specifically, improving satisfaction can not only directly enhance brand building effectiveness but also further promote the success of the brand by enhancing the impact of organizational operations and market promotion. Therefore, enterprises should focus on and improve customer and employee satisfaction to achieve better brand building results.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study underscores the significant and positive impact of organizational operations, marketing activities, and market competition on the branding of sports events, with a particular focus on Emei Wushu. The research has successfully identified and validated a model that

highlights the key factors influencing the development and branding of Emei Wushu event activities. The findings emphasize the crucial mediating role of participant or spectator satisfaction in linking organizational operations, marketing promotions, and competitive events to effective brand building. Through extensive literature review and analysis of survey data from 454 participants using structural equation modeling techniques, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of how these factors interplay to shape the branding outcomes of Emei Wushu.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following brand development strategies are proposed:

5.2.1 Leverage National Intangible Cultural Heritage

Utilize the status of Emei Wushu as a national intangible cultural heritage to build a distinctive "Emei Wushu" brand. This involves promoting the cultural and historical significance of Emei Wushu, positioning it as a cultural treasure that embodies the rich heritage and values of Chinese wushu.

5.2.2 Develop Specialty Tourism

Integrate wushu with tourism to create a "Specialty Tourism" brand. This strategy aims to attract tourists interested in wushu and cultural experiences, thereby boosting the local economy and enhancing the visibility of Emei Wushu. Combining wushu events with tourism packages can create unique cultural experiences that draw in a global audience.

5.2.3 Promote the Emei wushu Cultural Industry

Establish the "Emei wushu Cultural Industry" brand to drive regional economic development. This includes creating and promoting cultural products and services related to Emei Wushu, organizing cultural events, and fostering a vibrant cultural industry that supports the growth and sustainability of Emei Wushu. The cultural industry can encompass various activities such as wushu performances, training workshops, and cultural exhibitions.

5.2.4 Enhance Organizational Operations and Marketing Efforts

Focus on improving the efficiency and effectiveness of organizational operations and marketing activities to boost participant satisfaction and brand loyalty. Implementing best practices in management and innovative marketing techniques will further strengthen the brand. This includes leveraging social media marketing, enhancing consumer engagement, and adopting integrated marketing communication strategies.

These strategies provide valuable insights for practitioners and researchers, offering practical guidance to enhance the international development of Emei Wushu and similar cultural events. By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can ensure the sustainable growth and global recognition of Emei Wushu as a premier wushu brand.

References

- 1) Song, T., & Luo, P. (2011). The Predicament and Solution of Emei Martial Arts Industry Development from the Perspective of Intangible Cultural Heritage. (pp. 63-66).
- 2) Zhang, Y., & Li, C. (2008). Research on the Characteristics and Development Prospects of Emei Martial Arts. (pp. 103-105).
- 3) Zhao, H., & Yao, W. (2012). Research on the Problems and Countermeasures Facing the Development of Emei Martial Arts. (pp. 78-81).
- 4) Zhang, X. (2009). Thoughts on the Development and Industrialization of Emei Martial Arts Cultural Resources. (pp. 182-186).
- 5) Xiong, X., & Qing, G. (2010). Research on the Impact of the International Emei Martial Arts Festival on Emei Martial Arts. (pp. 399-402).
- 6) Wang, M., Li, W., Zhang, F., & Tao, S. (2016). Research on the Construction and Application of Regional Martial Arts Culture Brand: Taking Sichuan Emei Martial Arts as an Example. (pp. 60-64).
- 7) Ma, D., Jiang, Y., & Zhu, M. (2015). Research on the Spatial Distribution of Chinese Sports Intangible Cultural Heritage Based on GIS. (pp. 19-24).
- 8) Yang, H., Wang, Y., & Zhang, F. (2023). Analysis of Factors Affecting Lifestyle Brands with Sustainable Fabrics Based on SEM. *Art and Design: Theory Edition*, 3, 92-94.
- 9) Shi, B. (2007). Research on the Construction of Theoretical System of Sports Geography. (pp. 3-24).
- 10) Reese, J. (2023). Rugged and Exciting: Examining the Personality of a Mixed Martial Arts Brand. (pp. 101-116).
- 11) Kim, H. R., & Koo, K. B. (2017). The Relationship between Brand Confidence of Martial Arts Competitions, Host City Image, and Attitude: Focusing on the 2016 Cheongju World Martial Arts Masterships. (Vol. 69, pp. 129-140).
- 12) Kim, H. R., Choi, Y. S., & Koo, K. B. (2016). The Relationship between Brand Attitude, Satisfaction, and Behavioral Intention in the Experience Program of the Chungju World Martial Arts Festival. (Vol. 64, pp. 443-454).
- 13) Dakroub, R., Issa, H., & Blumrodt, J. (2023). Predicting MMA Leagues' Fan Involvement through Its Brand Credibility and League-Brand Associations. (pp. 1-19).
- 14) Chen, Q., Wang, J., & Li, J. (2014). Analysis of the Brand Building of the "China-ASEAN Martial Arts Festival". (pp. 91-95).
- 15) Lee, S. M., & Lee, J. W. (2013). Structural Relationship Among Brand Image, Brand Attitude, and Loyalty in Coffee Shops. (pp. 55-65).
- 16) Kim, G. B., & Kim, B. G. (2016). Relationship among Brand Value Propositions, Brand Attitude, and Brand Attachment Considering Consumer Involvement. (pp. 103-111).
- 17) Kong, H., & Zhang, B. (2023). Research on the Development of Emei Martial Arts from the Perspective of Regional Culture. *Science, Education, and Culture*, 13, 185-188.
- 18) Zhang, Y. (2021). Research on the Integration and Development of Emei Martial Arts and Regional Cultural Tourism Industry. *Martial Arts Research*, 6(2), 41-43.
- 19) Wang, B., & Li, X. (2021). Research on the Development Predicament of Emei Martial Arts from the Perspective of Cultural Integration. *Sports Goods and Technology*, 15, 1-3.
- 20) Xu, S. (2021). Research on the Development Path of Emei Martial Arts Culture under the Background of a Sports Power. *Boxing and Fighting*, 3, 100-101.